

THE PROBLEM OF TEACHING STUDENTS LEXICAL AND PHRASEOLOGICAL FEATURES IN TRANSLATION STUDIES OF PHRASAL VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In modern English, the number of combinations of postpositions with verbs is especially large. Their number is steadily growing. This is evidenced by books and dictionaries devoted to phrasal verbs and their use. Along with the increase in number, the frequency of their use also increases. This indicates that they perform the necessary function, due to greater conciseness and, at the same time, greater expressiveness. The purpose of the article is to determine how often phrasal verbs are found in our daily life, and their diversity both in their compatibility and in the additional meanings that they contain or that they acquire in the text.

Introduction. In modern English, postpositions enter into a very large number of combinations of different types. The number of combinations, one of the components of which is a postposition, has been continuously increasing in English since the beginning of the New Anglican period and continues to grow.

Phrasal verbs are widely used not only in colloquial English [1]. Many of these verbs have become an integral part of the language of newspapers, law and economics. This is explained by the fact that many phrasal verbs have changed "their face" over time, that is, they have moved from one stylistic layer to another, acquired new meanings and lost old ones. Some phrasal verbs have received more frequent use than "simple" verbs, which are their synonyms.

Methods. Jane Povey gives the following definition of a phrasal verb. A phrasal verb is a combination of a "simple" verb (consisting of one word) [2].

For example: *come in - kirmoq*

give up - to'xtamoq

The definition of a phrasal verb causes much debate among linguists. Jane Povey, confirming her definition, identified the following characteristic features of a phrasal verb [3]:

A phrasal verb can be replaced by a "simple" verb. This characterizes the phrasal verb as a semantic unity:

call up - telephone, come by - obtain,

put off - postpone, put up with - tolerate.

But this criterion is not common to all phrasal verbs, since the equivalent of many phrasal verbs is a phrase [4]:

break down - stop functioning,

make up - apply cosmetics,

take off - of a plane - leave the ground.

The next feature is idiomaticity. By idiom we mean a combination of 2 or more words, the meaning of which does not coincide with the meaning of the components.

Results. Many phrasal verbs have a meaning that cannot be deduced from the meanings of its components.

For example: *bring up - educate*

give up - stop doing, using, etc.

go off - explode; ring

come by - obtain

But this criterion is also not common to all phrasal verbs, in addition, it is difficult to determine whether the meaning of the verb is idiomatic [5]. For example, the verbs fall down and pull off, on the one hand, do not have an idiomatic meaning.

fall down – yiqilmoq, tushmoq

pull off – olib tashlamoq.

But these verbs also have such dictionary meanings.

fall down - 1) to bow down (to someone in power)

2) to fail, to end unsuccessfully

pull off - 1) to achieve, despite difficulties

2) to win (a prize, a competition)

So, this property is not the main one for phrasal verbs, because sometimes the meaning of a verb can be deduced from its components [11].

Discussion. Some phrasal verbs have 2 or more meanings, some of which are idiomatic, while others, on the contrary, are easily deduced from the components.

2) Many linguists consider the ability of phrasal verbs to form passive constructions as one of its main properties. Jane Povey defines it with the English term "passivization" [6].

For example:

Payments are limited to 10% each month.

This medicine must be measured out exactly.

The next property of a phrasal verb is the ability to place an adverbial postposition before and after the noun used with the verb. For an object, the final position carries a greater semantic load, so if the complement does not carry new or important information, it is usually located in interposition [10].

For example: *Call him up or call up him (not his sister).*

If the object is expressed in several words, it will most likely occupy the final position.

For example:

He put on the coat he had bought in Tashkent.

If the object is expressed by a pronoun, it is always in interposition.

For example:

He took his coat and put it on.

Phrasal verbs are very diverse both in their compatibility and in the additional meanings that they contain or that they acquire in the text. They can express the nature of an action - a transition from one state to another, an incentive to act, etc., but in all cases the action is

invariably characterized by the meaning contained in the verb itself [7]. A very numerous and diverse group is made up of phrasal verbs that express movement and at the same time characterize it. Verbs in this group most often express not just movement, but a transition from one place to another. Therefore, most of them are used with postpositions indicating the direction of movement (into, out, up, to) [9].

For example: *stand up - get up,*

go out - go out,

go into - enter,

jump into - jump up.

It is worth noting separately the cases when a phrasal verb expresses the cessation or, conversely, the beginning of movement.

For example: *get over - finish, deal with something.*

jump down - jump off.

run out - finish the race.

throw off, get off - start (something).

A very large group is made up of phrasal verbs expressing the transition of an object from one state to another or its movement [8].

In essence, verbs that express the transition from movement to immobility or the beginning of movement can be attributed to this group or considered as an intermediate link. In general, the boundaries between individual groups of phrasal verbs are very lexically fluid, so they are not easy to define.

Conclusion. So, completing the description of the properties and functions of postpositions, we can conclude the following. Postpositions are not morphological or syntactic units, but a lexical private subdivision of the vocabulary of the English language. Like other parts of speech and their subdivisions, for example nouns that can be subjects, complements, definitions, applications, predicative members or circumstances in sentences, they can perform different functions to varying degrees of independence. In addition, it should be noted that the number of postpositions attached to phrasal verbs directly depends on the spatial activity of the subject or object of the action. That is why there are most of them in verbs of motion, verbs of physical action and verbs of visual perception.

It is no exaggeration to say that the question of English phrasal verbs is one of the most important issues in the theoretical study and practical mastery of the English language. Phrasal verbs occupy a significant place in the verbal vocabulary of modern English and are extremely common due to their great diversity, idiomatic meanings and heterogeneity of functioning. The development and replenishment of the system of phrasal verbs occurs in two directions: the involvement of new verbs and the development of the semantics of already created language units.

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